

Preparation and Study of Hydroxytriazenes as Analytical Reagents. Part IV. 3-Hydroxy-1,3-*p*. ditolyltriazene as a Reagent for Palladium and Copper.

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Preparation and analytical usefulness of five methyl and two chloro substituted hydroxytriazenes have been described. Out of these compounds, 3-hydroxy-1,3-*p*. ditolyltriazene is found to be highly selective reagent for the gravimetric estimation of copper and palladium. It gives more stable complexes and has more favourable conversion factor than the unsubstituted hydroxytriazene.

In earlier Parts of this series¹⁻³, preparation and analytical usefulness of several hydroxytriazenes have been reported. In view of a very interesting and useful complex forming group, which this class of compounds has introduced, it has been considered worth while to extend this investigation. The present communication describes the study of five methyl and two chloro substituted hydroxytriazenes. Out of these compounds, 3-hydroxy-1,3-*p*. ditolyltriazene has been examined in detail as the complexes formed by this compound are very stable and the excess of the reagent used during precipitation hydrolyses in acidic medium to give water soluble products which can be easily eliminated by simple washing.

EXPERIMENTAL

The compounds were prepared by the method described in the Part I. Methyl substituted phenylhydroxyl-amines were prepared by reducing the corresponding methyl substituted nitrobenzene in 60% aqueous-alcoholic medium with zinc dust in presence of ammonium chloride. Similarly, the chlorosubstituted phenylhydroxyl-amines were prepared in 50% aqueous-alcoholic medium. These solutions were directly used for further reaction with benzene diazonium chloride or substituted benzene diazonium chloride at 0° to give corresponding hydroxytriazenes. Table I summarises the physical properties of these compounds.

Hydrolysability of the Compounds: Experiments were conducted as described in Part II to study the hydrolysis of these compounds in acidic medium. It was found that all methyl substituted hydroxytriazenes (Compounds I to V) hydrolyse to yield water-soluble products while the chlorosubstituted compounds (VI and VII) do not yield water-soluble products. Hence any excess of the reagent used during precipitation of metal

1. Sogani and Bhattacharya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **36**, 563.
2. Gupta, Jain and Sogani, *ibid.*, 1960, **37**, 531.
3. Gupta and Sogani, *ibid.*, 1961, **38**, 771.

TABLE I

Compound.	Crystallised form	M.P.	Crystal shape	Analysis (in %)				
				C	H	N	Cl	
C_6H_5	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3(\text{O})$	50% water mixture	66°	Light Yellow needles	found 68.61 Calc. 68.72	5.68 5.78	18.69 18.80	—
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3(\text{O})$	C_6H_5	do	79°	Yellow needles	found 68.64 Calc. 68.72	5.64 5.73	18.58 18.50	—
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3(\text{p})$	C_6H_5	95% Ethanol	125°	Light yellow needles	found 68.56 Calc. 68.72	5.70 5.73	18.56 18.50	—
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3(\text{p})$	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3(\text{p})$	do	131°	Light yellow needles	found 69.54 Calc. 69.71	6.08 6.22	17.56 17.43	—
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3(\text{O})$	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3(\text{p})$	50% water-ethanol mixture	82°	Yellow needles	found 69.48 Calc. 69.71	6.11 6.22	17.61 17.43	—
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}(\text{p})$	C_6H_5	95% Ethanol	125°	Light yellow needles	found 58.08 Calc. 58.18	3.92 4.04	17.19 16.97	14.43 14.94
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}(\text{O})$	C_6H_5	50% Ethanol water	77°	Light yellow needles, decomposes in two days	found 57.98 Calc. 58.18	3.96 4.04	17.13 16.97	14.46 14.94

complexes, in cases of methyl-substituted hydroxytriazenes hydrolyse to give water-soluble products, and can be easily eliminated by simple washing, thus, leaving the metal complexes in the direct weighable forms.

Solutions: Standard palladium chloride and copper sulphate solutions and buffer solutions, etc. were prepared as described in Part II.

A Cambridge bench type pH Meter was used for pH measurements, and sintered glass No. 3 for collecting the precipitates.

Properties of Complexes: The palladium complex is yellowish-brown in colour, readily soluble in chloroform and benzene and fairly soluble in ether and acetone. It is only slightly soluble in alcohol. It was crystallised from acetone, m.p. 224°. Analysis, found: N, 16.34%; $(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_5\text{O})_2$ Pd requires N, 16.02.

The copper complex is chocolate-brown in colour. As regards solubility in organic solvents, it resembles palladium complex. It was crystallised from acetone, m.p. 195°. Analysis; found N, 15.14% $(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_5\text{O})_2$ Cu requires N, 15.44%.

Conditions for Quantitative Precipitation: Various determinations were done using varying amounts of the reagent under different pH conditions. It was found that palladium and copper were completely precipitated between pH 1.8 and 7.0 and 2.3 and 7.0 respectively with only 15 to 20% excess of the reagent. However, pH range between 2 and 3 was considered desirable as it increased the specificity of the reagent and facilitated removal of the excess reagent by hydrolysis.

Procedure for Palladium: A solution of palladium containing 6 to 40 mg. of the metal is diluted to about 120 c.c. 10% sodium acetate or sodium potassium tartrate (w/v, 2-3 c.c.) and N-HCl (2 c.c.) are added to it so as to bring pH of the solution at 2.0-3.0. It is

warmed and 1% ethanolic solution of the reagent (about 20% excess) is added with constant stirring. Palladium complex separates as a dirty green precipitate. It is heated on a boiling water bath for about an hour, during which period the precipitate changes its colour to yellowish-brown and becomes granular. The supernatant liquid also becomes clear. It is filtered hot through a weighed sintered glass crucible No. 3, washed with hot water 3 to 4 times till the washings do not give yellow colour with a drop of NaOH solution. The complex is dried to a constant weight at 120-30°. It takes about half an hour. The results are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Pd taken	Foreign ion	Pd Complex	Pd found	Error
0 mg.	—	·0332 g	6.02 mg.	0.02 mg.
12	—	·0663	12.02	0.02
18	—	·0993	18.0	—0.00
12	Ni ²⁺ , ·1g	·0661	11.98	—0.02
12	Co ²⁺ , ·1	·0663	12.02	0.02
12	Cd ²⁺ , ·1	·0664	12.04	0.04
12	Zn ²⁺ , ·1	·0660	11.96	—0.04
12	Mn ²⁺ , ·1	·0661	11.98	—0.02
12	Fe ²⁺ , ·1	·0661	11.98	—0.02
12	Fe ³⁺ , ·1	·0665	12.06	0.06
12	V ⁴⁺ , ·1	·0663	12.02	0.02
12	Zr ⁴⁺ , ·1	·0663	12.02	0.02
12	Sb ³⁺ , ·1	·0661	11.98	—0.02
12	Bi ³⁺ , ·1	·0663	12.02	0.02
12	Ce ⁴⁺ , ·1	·0660	11.96	—0.04
12	Cr ³⁺ , ·1	·0663	12.02	0.02
12	Be ²⁺ , ·1	·0661	11.98	—0.02
12	Molybdate, ·1	·0661	11.98	—0.02
12	Tungstate, ·1	·0661	11.98	—0.02
12	Hg ²⁺ , ·1	·0664	12.04	0.04
12	As ³⁺ , ·1	·0665	12.06	0.06
12	U ₆ ³⁺ , ·1	·0663	12.02	0.02

The interference due to Fe²⁺, Fe³⁺, Ti⁴⁺ and molybdate was eliminated by adding 0.5 g. of sodium fluoride as a masking agent. The hydrolysis of Sn⁴⁺ and Zr⁴⁺ was also prevented as given above, and that of Ce⁴⁺ by adding a small amount of solid ammonium sulphate. In case of Bi³⁺ and Sb³⁺ sodium potassium tartrate was used as a buffering agent.

Procedure for Copper: The procedure adopted for determining copper is the same as given above. The solution may contain 10 to 30 mg. of copper. Table III records the results obtained.

The properties and stabilities of palladium and copper complexes are very similar. Hence observations recorded in case of palladium in presence of foreign ions are also applicable in the case of copper. For the sake of brevity all these have not been included here.

TABLE III

Cu taken	Foreign ion	Cu Complex	Cu found	Error
10 mg.	—	·0858 g.	10·02 mg.	0·02 mg.
20	—	·1712	19·99	—0·01
30	—	·2571	30·03	0·03
10	Co ⁺⁺ , 0·1g	·0858	10·02	0·02
10	Ni ⁺⁺ , 0·1	·0855	9·99	—0·01
10	Zn ⁺⁺ , 0·1	·0859	10·03	0·03
10	Mn ⁺⁺ , 0·1	·0861	10·05	0·05
10	Cd ⁺⁺ , 0·1	·0858	10·02	0·02
10	Hg ⁺⁺ , 0·1	·0854	9·98	—0·02
10	Fe ⁺⁺ , 0·1	·0857	10·01	0·01
10	Fe ³⁺ , 0·1	·0860	10·04	0·04
10	Cr ³⁺ , 0·1	·0858	10·02	0·02
10	Al ³⁺ , 0·1	·859	10·03	0·03
10	Bi ³⁺ , 0·1	·0855	9·99	—0·01
10	Sb ³⁺ , 0·1	·0857	10·01	0·01
10	Molybdate 0·1	·0858	10·02	0·02

DISCUSSION

3-Hydroxy-1, 3-*p*.ditolyltriazene has a distinct advantage over the parent compound, namely, 3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene⁴ which has been claimed to be superior to the conventional reagents employed for the gravimetric determination of palladium and copper. Table IV gives the stabilities and conversion factors for palladium and copper complexes of these two compounds. The stabilities were determined in 70% dioxan-water mixture by employing Bjerrum-Calvin pH titration technique⁵.

TABLE IV

Compound	Palladium Complex		Copper Complex	
	Stability (log K)	Conversion factor	Stability (log K)	Conversion factor
3-Hydroxy-1, 3-diphenyltriazene	22·66	·2009	22·31	·1903
3-Hydroxy-1, 3- <i>p</i> .ditolyltriazene	24·23	·1813	23·95	·1168

A comparison of the values given in the Table IV will reveal that the complexes of ditolyl derivative have more favourable stabilities and conversion factors than those of

4. Sogani and Bhattacharya, *Anal. Chem.*, 1956, 28, 81, 1616.

5. Calvin and Melander, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70.

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the parent compound. The increased stability of the methyl substituted hydroxytriazene metal complexes over those of parent hydroxytriazene complexes is because of +I effect (electron pushing) of methyl groups. A hyperconjugative effect for the methyl group would also have similar effect.

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